

AI-Driven Risk Management in Construction: Integrating Digital Platforms with Financial Oversight

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Abbreviations:

ICT: Information, and communication technology; ECB: European Central Bank; AI: Artificial intelligence;

LSM: Least-squares method

Abstract

In this study, we explore risk management tools in construction projects, addressing prevalent issues such as deadline and budget overruns through the application of artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms. The traditional construction process often suffers from fragmentation where stakeholders operate in isolation, and construction sites distant from central management lead to inefficiencies, misunderstandings, and cost overruns. These challenges are compounded by the vast amount of data generated throughout a project's lifecycle and the difficulty in classifying this data to extract actionable insights for informed decision-making.

To address these issues, we integrate various digital technologies into the construction management process. This integration includes the use of computer vision and the Internet of Things (IoT) for data collection on resource usage, alongside machine learning algorithms for data clustering and AI for making predictive analyses. Such technological integration aims to enhance the speed and quality of decision-making.

Furthermore, we propose a mathematical polynomial regression model to predict construction project costs based on data from completed projects and their technical characteristics. This model utilizes the least squares method to select analogues by minimizing the sum of squared deviations between actual and predicted values. The model's effectiveness is assessed through the coefficient of determination, which measures the correlation between the dependent variable (project budget) and independent variables (technical characteristics and resource costs), thereby validating the model's accuracy in forecasting project costs.

Keywords: project management; cost management; digitalization; construction; artificial intelligence

1. Introduction

Globally, the construction industry is prone to economic and operational risks, as reflected in the delayed commissioning of projects and overspending of the initial budget. A 2022 business research report states that “the bridge construction market is expected to grow to \$1,095.61 billion in 2026 at an average CAGR of 5.4%” [1]. “Approximately 90% of transportation network projects have high completion costs compared to their original budgets, resulting in rising costs [2]. Several high-profile transportation projects worldwide have experienced cost overruns” [3]. The literature contains many examples and information about cost overrun projects, for instance, in Germany: “Among the completed projects, the ECB was built three years later than planned. With a cost overrun of 48%, the Elbphilharmonie was completed seven years later, and the cost rose “like yeast,” exceeding 1025%. Megaprojects Berlin 1/large-scale projects often cost more than USD 1 billion. Projects in other sectors, such as defense, information, and communication technology (ICT), exceed this amount. 4 Brandenburg (Germany) and Stuttgart 21 are still in progress. Since Stuttgart 21 was launched in April 1994, it has been amended several times regarding the total cost and completion date. It is scheduled to open by 2025, six years later than planned, and cost overruns are currently approximately 228%.” [4]. Table 1 presents the results of the research on budget overruns.

Table 1. Incidence of overruns and the magnitude of overruns based on an analysis of the literature [5]

Study	Geography	Case frequency (%)	Overran sum*			
			Automobile Road		Rail Road	
			%	N	%	N
Merewitz (1973)	US	79	26	49	54	17

Morris (1990)	India	86			164	23
Pickrell (1990, 1992)	US				61	8
Auditor General (1994)	Sweden	5	86	8		
Bordat et al. (2004)	US	8	5	2668		
Odeck (2004)	Norway	52	8	620		
Dantata et al. (2006)	US	81			30	16
Ellis et al. (2007)	US		9	3130		
Lee (2008)	South Korea	95	11	138	48	16
Flyvbjerg et al. (2003a)	World	86	20	167	41	58
European Central Bank (ECB) (2009)	Germany		48			

* %: percentage of cost overruns and N: number of projects with cost overruns.

Assuming an expected bridge construction market size of \$1095.61 billion in 2026, the incidence of cost overruns on 86% of projects globally, and an average cost overrun of 20% of the original budget, it is estimated that the total cost overruns for bridge construction alone in the world could be \$188.445 billion in 2026.

Many studies on initial budget overruns aim to identify the causes and develop cost management mechanisms to achieve project success, which is critical in highly competitive and unstable economies [6-8]. Project success involves creating a construction product with the necessary technical characteristics to meet user needs. It is implemented within an established budget and provides positive financial results to all participants in the construction process.

According to most researchers, a project typically fails due to failure to meet the planned schedule, budget, and quality requirements [9, 10]. One of the main reasons for

bridge construction cost overruns is the inadequate estimation of design and construction costs [11-13]. The reasons for the failure to meet schedule, budget, and quality may be circumstances that cannot be foreseen and accounted for at the design stage because construction is performed outdoors under changing weather conditions [14]. It is impossible to predict the behavior of soils during foundation construction, exclude errors at the design stage, or avoid defects while working. Many studies have also focused on finding solutions to reduce the cost of facility construction, such as using new technologies for work production, innovative materials, and optimizing the design, construction, and project management processes.

Notably, most studies on bridge construction cost overruns have been conducted in developed countries such as the USA, Canada, Japan, Germany, and the United Kingdom (UK). However, this phenomenon is also relevant in developing countries, where infrastructure projects often face limited budgets and lack design and construction expertise. Consequently, understanding which risk management techniques lead to project success, which factors give rise to risks, how to monitor these factors, and how to adjust schedules and budgets operationally are critical for enriching construction management knowledge.

2. Literature review

This study reviews articles with recent advancements in digital technologies, particularly AI and ML, what opened new avenues for addressing challenges in construction data. These technologies offer promising tools for enhancing accuracy in cost predictions, improving risk management, and optimizing project execution strategies.

Aslam et al.'s [15] study uses Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), time series, and linear regression to predict the Construction Cost Index (CCI) for building materials in developing countries. They particularly emphasize the performance of the ANN model, which

outperformed other methods in terms of prediction accuracy. AI models, specifically ANNs, provided superior accuracy in forecasting construction costs, highlighting their potential in handling complex, nonlinear data typical in economic forecasting. Researches is more specialized in its focus on the predictive capabilities of AI in estimating the CCI, an essential factor in the construction industry of developing nations.

Park and Yun [16] found that using BIM attributes alongside deep learning reduces the prediction error rates compared to using conventional methods or BIM attributes alone. Their study underscores the potential of combining detailed architectural data with sophisticated AI algorithms to enhance early-stage cost estimations.

Pai and Wang [17] utilize machine learning models including least squares support vector regression (LSSVR), classification and regression tree (CART), general regression neural networks (GRNN), and backpropagation neural networks (BPNN) for real estate price prediction. They focus on using actual transaction data to enhance prediction accuracy, with LSSVR providing superior results compared to other models. This study emphasizes the importance of accurate model tuning using genetic algorithms for parameter selection.

The article "Development of a Capital Expenditure Model in the Context of Construction Digitalization" by Arkadij N. Larionov, Vyacheslav V. Solovev, and Alexander A. Morozov [18], addresses the challenges and necessities of integrating digital technologies into the capital expenditure planning processes within the construction industry. The study explores how the digitalization discrepancies between state policies and practical implementations in construction hinder effective project execution. It emphasizes the development of a digital pricing subsystem within the project information model to facilitate consistent government and contractor interactions concerning cost estimations. This research aims to bridge the gap between theoretical digitalization strategies and their practical application, ensuring that cost data is accessible and manageable across all stakeholders,

thereby enhancing transparency and efficiency in construction project cost management. The findings suggest a move towards unified methodological approaches to cost calculations to support a large-scale transition to information modeling in construction.

The article titled "Development of a Capital Expenditure Model in the Context of Construction Digitalization" by Arkadij N. Larionov, Vyacheslav V. Solovev, and Alexander A. Morozov [19] explores the challenges and opportunities of integrating digital technologies into capital expenditure planning in construction. It emphasizes the discrepancies between theoretical digitalization strategies and their practical application, hindering effective project execution. The paper advocates for the development of a digital pricing subsystem within the project information model, aimed at facilitating consistent and transparent interactions between government bodies and contractors regarding cost estimations. This study underscores the need for a unified approach to cost calculations and methodological consistency to support a comprehensive transition to digital information modeling in construction, highlighting the potential for enhancing transparency and efficiency in managing construction project costs.

These articles collectively demonstrate the versatility of AI and machine learning in construction and real estate, showing how different approaches can be tailored to meet various industry needs from project management to material testing and property pricing. Each study contributes uniquely to the broader understanding of how digital technologies can transform traditional industries by providing more accurate predictions and efficient resource management. Some studies highlight the potential of AI and digital technologies in enhancing the prediction and management of construction costs.

By comparing these approaches, this study seeks to highlight the diverse potential of AI and ML in revolutionizing cost management practices in the construction sector. The findings will not only provide insights into the effectiveness of various models and algorithms but also

discuss the practical implications and limitations of these technologies in real-world applications. Article discusses a broader range of digital technologies including the Internet of Things (IoT) and computer vision, alongside artificial intelligence. The focus here is on a polynomial regression model to predict the costs of construction projects, which is fine-tuned through the least-squares method to minimize prediction errors. This comprehensive analysis aims to guide future research directions and inform industry practitioners about adopting these technologies for enhanced decision-making and project management.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Factor analysis influencing the cost of a construction project

The cost or budget for facility construction estimates the expenses required to complete a construction project, including the inputs of materials, labor, equipment, engineering, and technical solutions, as well as other costs associated with the construction process. Therefore, the design of the algorithm is inextricably linked to analyzing the costs and expenses involved, past project data containing information on the amount of resources spent on each project, their cost and technical characteristics, evaluating factors, and identifying patterns and trends that influence the outcomes of completed projects.

To itemize the information at its creation time, we used the approach described by ISO 19650 [20] and national standards such as BS 1192:2007+A2:2016 [21] in the UK and DIN EN ISO 19650-2:2019 [22] in Germany. These standards define detailed levels for each stage of a facility's life cycle, from conceptual design to operation, depending on the level of project development.

Level 1 (LOD 100): Concept Preparatory Phase: This phase determines the total project cost based on the initial data, where we use an estimate based on a comparison with similar projects or expert judgments.

Level 2 (LOD 200) and Level 3 (LOD 300)—Design and Construction Document

Updating: This stage involves updating the cost information based on more accurate data. This information can be obtained from design documents, progress reports, and specialist consultations.

Level 4 (LOD 400)—Work Plan Adjustment: This stage involves adjusting the cost of work based on changes in the project or work conditions—for example, a change in lead time, scope of work, or prices of materials and equipment.

Level 5 (LOD 500): Construction Documents (actual): This step involves determining the work value based on the work performed and the costs incurred, including verifying the actual material, labor, and equipment rental costs.

We compare the actual costs throughout the construction period with the expected costs. If the actual costs exceed the expected limits, it is necessary to promptly analyze and make several management decisions related to adjusting actions at the construction site and forming a plan of measures for further avoidance and prevention.

For the analysis, information was grouped according to time, construction objects, and cost items. Figure 1 shows an example of the accumulation of cost information at various

stages of construction project realization.

Figure 1. Construction project cost information accumulation stages.

A list of the required data should be compiled and organized from various sources (e.g., design documents, estimates, material prices, and accounting systems) to collect and classify the data according to cost items and projects. As the data are from different sources, they have different titles, requiring them to be classified into a single table or program to calculate the total construction cost.

Construction cost data should be structured according to the characteristics for which analog selection and cost forecasting are planned.

Table 2 presents an example of structuring the construction cost data based on cost items.

- Materials: A list of all materials required, including quantities, units of measurement, and unit cost.
- Personnel: calculation of workers' and specialists' labor costs, including the number of hours worked and cost per hour;
- Machinery: List of machine hours used and cost per hour by machine type
- Equipment: List of equipment required, including the cost of renting or purchasing it
- Overhead: costs of construction organization, utilities, etc.

Table 2. Matrix of costs for the construction of facilities

Project title	Groups of construction costs, i.e.						Construction contract cost of works, c.u.
	materials (M)	Personnel (L)	Vehicles (MM)	equipment (E)	overhead costs (Cost)	Profit	
Construction and Assembly Section No.1							
Construction and Assembly Section No.2							
Construction and Assembly Section No.3							
Construction and Assembly Section No.4							

Construction and Assembly Section No...							
Construction and Assembly Section No...							

Based on this information, a matrix can be created, where each column corresponds to a separate cost group and each row corresponds to a separate project. We consolidated all budgets into a single matrix, with information grouped horizontally by cost group and vertically by company project. Before processing the data, it was necessary to conduct a preliminary analysis using statistical methods, such as correlation and variance analyses, to determine the most significant factors affecting project costs. Their budgets should be represented as vectors that should be compared to determine the closest cost combinations for projects. A separate element of the vector represents each cost, and its value is equal to the cost. Table 1 presents an example of accumulating information on project construction costs for subsequent presentations in vector form.

Structuring information in this manner and constantly updating it allowed us to create a database of actual costs that could be used for project construction costs. To test this hypothesis, we hypothesized that using artificial intelligence and multiple regression would create an effective cost-forecasting model.

3.2. Multiple regression equation and artificial intelligence as an algorithm for predicting the cost of construction projects

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a field of computer science that develops algorithms and programs that enable computers to perform tasks that require human intelligence.

A multiple regression equation is a mathematical model that analyzes and describes the relationship between a dependent variable and several independent variables.

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \dots + b_pX_p + E \quad (1)$$

a – free factor

b_i - partial angular coefficient for the dependence of Y on X

p – number of model parameters

E – varying vector Y

We first transformed the multiple regression equation, taking the value of the variable as the size of the cost (budget) for the construction of the object and the independent variables as the values of the parameters affecting the cost. One parameter affecting the cost is the amount of resources needed to build an object and its price. The resource method determines the costs. Thus, we expressed the cost through a multiple regression equation in the form of the sum of the products of the unit price of a resource and its quantity distributed over the time of work performance (Formula 2).

$$C(t) = P + \sum_{t=1}^t (M_i \cdot V_{mi} + Log_i \cdot t_{mi} + L_i \cdot V_{li} \cdot t_{li} + MM_i \cdot V_{mmi} \cdot t_{mmi} + E_i \cdot V_{ei} \cdot t_{ei} + Cost \cdot t_c + Int \cdot K \cdot t_{int}) \quad (2)$$

where $C(t)$ – total amount of the budget for construction and installation works, units,

i – number of operations that must be performed to complete all work;

M_i is the cost per unit of one unit of material required to produce the i th type of work.

V_{mi} the quantity of materials for each i th type of work, measured in units.

Log_i – Cost of delivery and storage of one unit of material or equipment per hour, in units

t_{mi} – time required for the storage and delivery of materials, h

L_i – cost of one person-hour of personnel labor depending on its qualification for the production of the i-th type of work, units;

V_{li} – number of personnel labor units for each ith type of work (person-hours).

t_{li} – Duration of personnel work, person-hours

MM_i – Cost of 1 h of machine work and mechanisms for the production of the ith type of work (units)

V_{mmi} is the number of machine units and mechanisms for each i-th type of work and machine hour.

t_{mmi} is the working time of the machines and mechanisms for each ith type of work in machine hours.

E_i is the cost of 1 h of operation of equipment, scaffolding, and other inventory structures for the production of the ith type of work in units.

V_{ei} is the number of pieces of equipment, scaffolding, and other inventory structures for each ith type of work and machine hour.

t_{ei} is the working time of the equipment, scaffolding, and other inventory structures for each ith type of work, in machine hours.

$Cost_t$ – Overhead costs incurred by companies regardless of the quantity of products produced and sold (e.g., management expenses, security of the facility, IT), units

t_{cost} – object construction period for calculating overhead costs (months).

Int_t – costs of servicing the company's capital involved in turnover (the shorter the cycle "money - goods - money," the faster the return of capital into turnover and, consequently, the lower the costs of its servicing, and vice versa) %;

K is the amount of diverted capital for construction financing and the payment of advances to suppliers, contractors, and units.

t_{int} – Period of facility construction for calculating capital maintenance costs in months.

Where P is the contractor's expected profit. Profit is a fixed amount or percentage of the planned cost of production, indicating the dependence of profit on the construction duration of the object and cost units.

Comparing Eqs. (1) and (2), the sought value of the budget size $C(t)$ can be expressed through Y as a multiple regression using Eq. (2), where the free term (a) is profit, variable X is the number of resources needed for construction (materials, machinery, etc.), the number of parameters (p) is the number of resource sets, and the private angular coefficient (b_i) is the unit cost of the resource.

We group the variables in Eq. (1) into five main sets of resources (the number of parameters $p = \text{five}$).

Materials (M)

Personnel (L)

machinery (MM)

Equipment (E)

Overhead costs ($Cost$).

The project budget can be represented as a matrix, where each plane represents a separate resource and the values on the planes denote the costs of this resource, which are calculated as the product of the price of the resource (on one axis) and the quantity of these resources (on the other axis). Thus, each matrix element represents the cost of a particular resource at a specific point in time. That is, the total size of the construction budget is an n -

dimensional matrix depending on the quantity and price of the planned resources and their usage time at the site, which are difficult to predict under constant changes. The values in the matrix represent the quantity of resources required to produce work and their prices. As the example in Eq. (2), to calculate the material costs (M) depending on the quantity of resources and their prices, we use a matrix of dimension $n \times 2$, where n is the number of resources. The first and second columns of the matrix contain the numbers of units used for each resource and their prices, respectively. Each matrix element is denoted by a_{ij} , where i is the number of resources and $j=1$ or $j=2$ is the number of columns. The matrix can have dimension $n \times 3$ to calculate labor costs; the first column is the number of resources, the second is the price, and the third is the unit cost.

Therefore, the matrices described in the example take the form of Eq. (3):

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} M_{m11} & V_{m12} \\ \dots & \dots \\ M_{mn1} & V_{mn2} \end{bmatrix} (3) \quad L = \begin{bmatrix} L_{11} & V_{l21} & t_{l31} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ L_{1n} & V_{l2n} & t_{l3n} \end{bmatrix} (3)$$

Because many types of resources are used in construction, there should be a separate matrix for each type of resource, specifying the number of units used for the resource and its price. Suppose that the prices of resources or other parameters, such as the quantity of resources, change; creating a new matrix with updated parameters is necessary to correctly estimate the cost and quantity of resources used in a particular period. To predict project costs, it is necessary to use a model that accounts for data on material costs, labor costs, and equipment rentals from different matrices. We performed cross-validation and error estimation to verify the accuracy of the models. If a model provides high forecasting accuracy, it can optimize the costs of new projects and improve a company's business processes.

Thus, in the context of data analytics and machine learning, a multiple regression equation can create machine learning models that can predict the values of the dependent variable (cost) based on the values of the independent variables (technical parameters and resources). Artificial intelligence can automatically create models based on large amounts of data.

We used the least-squares method (LSM) to select the analogs. The LSM can determine the closest match regarding budget and other project characteristics. The LSM estimates the parameters of the multivariate model and minimizes the sum of squares of the differences between the observed and predicted values. This method determines the linear or nonlinear function that best describes the relationship between variables, which is a set of values assumed to be calculated using a multiple regression equation (see Eqs. 1 and 2).

Graphs were used to visualize the dependence between variables. Because there are several variables, we represent the graph as a multidimensional surface, where each axis corresponds to one of the variables, and the height of a point on the surface corresponds to the value of the function at that point. Graphing tools such as three-dimensional graphs or color-scale graphs are used to represent multivariate surfaces. For example, for the three-dimensional graph presented in Figure 2, we can use the Matplotlib library in Python [23].

Figure 2: An example of a three-dimensional graph using a color scale created using the Matplotlib library in Python.

For each point on the plane, it is necessary to perform a cross-sectional analysis and derive a linear equation that represents the regression equation for this point; that is, the multiple regression in Eq. (2) can be represented as the sum of the individual y-values (Eq. (4)).

$$y = a + bx \quad (4)$$

where y is the value of the dependent variable (the sum of costs - budget), x is the value of the independent variable (the project characteristic, for example, the number of units of the resource "concrete"), a is the free term (for example, the price premium "profit"), and b is the slope coefficient of the straight line (for example, the price per unit of the resource "concrete").

The cost calculation equation using linear regression in Eq. (2) in the form of the sum of the individual values of y (4) is as follows:

$$C(t) = P + \sum_{t=1}^t (M_i \cdot V_{mi} + Log_i \cdot t_{mi} + L_i \cdot V_{li} \cdot t_{li} + MM_i \cdot V_{mmi} \cdot t_{mmi} + E_i \cdot V_{ei} \cdot t_{ei} + Cost \cdot t_c + Int \cdot K \cdot t_{int}) = y_m + y_l + y_{mm} + y_e + y_{cost} + y_{int} \quad (5)$$

In this case, the coefficients in Eq. (4), and the values from Eq. (5), Pi, b is the unit cost of the resource and x is the number of resource units.

Therefore, we transform the value calculation equation into a set of linear equations that represent the matrices of the values. For further cost forecasting based on analogs, it is necessary to select the closest value yi from the available database separately for each parameter and calculate the cost by summing them. The closest values were selected using the least squares method. For example, Figure 3 shows a set of budget values (y) for different types of work depending on their number (b*x) and coefficient a. Minimizing the sum of the

squares of the deviations of the real values of y from the forecasted values of y on a straight line is necessary to select the most similar object from the actual set in which budget forecasting was performed. This can be achieved by using the least-squares method (Eq. (6)).

$$MSE(a, b) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - a - bx_i)^2, \tag{6}$$

where MSE is the mean square error and is the mean value of the square of the difference between the actual and predicted values during model testing, as shown in Figure 3. It was used to assess the accuracy of the model; the smaller the MSE, the more accurate the model.

Once the values of a and b are determined, a straight-line equation can deliver the budget values for any project characteristic.

Figure 3: Model accuracy estimation using the least squares method.

Thus, LSM selects analogs when predicting the cost of investment projects using artificial intelligence by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations between the actual and predicted values. For this purpose, we first built a mathematical model to describe the relationship between the independent variables (e.g., project characteristics) and the dependent variable (construction cost). We then trained the model using the available data and LSM to analyze the deviations between the actual and predicted values and adjusted the model to minimize these deviations.

Once model training is complete, the cost of investment projects can be predicted by entering the values of the characteristics into the model, which produces the predicted cost.

3.3. Model quality assessment based on the calculation of the coefficient of determination

The use of the least-squares method to predict the construction costs of peer-based projects may be limited by data quality and model accuracy. Therefore, it is necessary to further analyze the data and verify the accuracy of the model before using it to predict construction costs.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) indicates how well LSM fits the dependent variable (budget) for forecasting. This measures the proportion of variance in the dependent variable (budget) explained by the model's independent variables (technical specifications, resources, etc.). The value of R^2 ranges between 0 and 1, where 0 and 1 indicate that the model does not explain the variation in the data but fits the data perfectly. The closer the R^2 value is to 1, the better the model explains the data. The coefficient of determination (R^2) using Eq. (7):

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{SS_{res}}{SS_{tot}} = 1 - \frac{\sum(y_f - y_p)^2}{\sum(y_f - \bar{y}_f)^2} \quad (7)$$

Где SS_{res} – sum of squares of residuals – the difference between the actual budget values calculated based on object analogs (y_f) and the projected budget value calculated by the model for the new facility (y_p), and

SS_{tot} the sum of the squares (the difference between the actual budget values calculated by the object analogs) (y_f) and their average values.

Thus, to build a model for predicting the construction project budget, the actual values of the dependent variable are data on the project costs or actual construction costs (material, equipment, labor, and other costs) that have been associated with similar projects in the past. We use these data to train the model and verify its accuracy in predicting budgets for future projects. We can judge the accuracy of the model using the coefficient of determination and standard error of the mean. If the accuracy of the model is insufficient, the data must be further analyzed and/or the selected factors must be changed.

3.4.Example of using multiple regression model to predict costs at different construction stages

An important question is: What characteristics can be used to predict budget values using the least-squares method? The deeper the stage of project development required for the project to be forecasted, the more characteristics are included in the multiple regression equation. Table 3 presents an example of using the equation $y = a + bx$ to predict the budget size for the construction of objects (using bridges as an example) depending on the stage of development.

Table 3. Example of using the equation $y = a + bx$ to predict the size of the budget for construction projects (bridges as an example) depending on their stage of development

project development stage	variables to project the size of the cost budget $y = a + bx^*$		Purpose (project objective)
	x	b	
Level 1 (LOD 100) – Conception.	area of the object; technical characteristics (metal bridge, reinforced concrete, etc.); geographical location, etc.	price per unit of the object-analog, source-accumulated statistical database	selection of the closest object analog by x-values and forecasting the cost of the future object (initial budget)
Level 2 (LOD 200) – project documentation	Structural design (piles, support, span, etc.)	price per unit of similar design - accumulated database of statistical data, planned prices	Refining the future value by specifying the criteria for selecting an analogy
Level 3 (LOD 300) – project documentation	resources as per work schedule; structural elements as per the project	scheduled pricing	Identifying the risk of overspending the initial budget; determining the planned size of the budget.

Level 4 (LOD 400) – work plan.	resources on schedule, supplier specifications, and acquisition plans	scheduled pricing	identifying the risk of budget overruns, predicting the result by considering adjustments to project decisions, determining the range of deviations
Level 5 (LOD 500) – executive documentation (actual)	actual resources utilized	Actual pricing	accumulation of data statistics, advanced analytics

* where:

Where y is the cost of constructing an object (budget) in units.

a is the shift coefficient, i.e., the price premium inflation, risk level, profit, etc.

Thus, information is continually updated and detailed as the project progresses through the LOD levels. To ensure continuous monitoring of changes within the original budget or “corridor of values,” it is necessary to establish links between documents provided by the names from the classifier at the top level.

LSM can be used at different levels of project development, depending on the goals and objectives. As shown in Figure 4, the following method can be used:

- At the preliminary stage (LOD100) for value forecasting based on object analogs.

- At the implementation stage (LOD300), the forecasted cost specification is based on similar types of studies.
- In the final stage (LOD500), plan-to-fact deviations were analyzed for overruns or underruns.

Figure 4: Example of using the least squares method for budget forecasting and creating an analytical system.

Thus, the LSM can predict the construction cost of objects based on analogs as follows:

1. Compile data on the construction cost of similar objects. The data can be obtained from public sources and databases or collected manually.
2. Identify factors affecting construction costs. Examples include the area of the facility, number of supports, and materials used in the construction.
3. A linear regression model was drawn using the least-squares method. Identifying the dependent and independent variables (construction costs) (factors affecting construction costs).
4. The accuracy of the model was assessed using the coefficient of determination and standard error of the mean. If the accuracy of the model is insufficient, further data analysis and/or modification of the selected factors are necessary.
5. Analyze the cost of building new facilities using the model constructed and the values of the independent variables for the new facilities.

This determined how accurately the budget was planned and the factors that led to deviations from the plan. Based on the results of the analysis, decisions can be made to optimize construction costs and improve future planning. Using the least-squares method to predict the data quality and model accuracy may limit the construction costs of facilities based on analogs. Therefore, it is necessary to further analyze the data and verify the accuracy of the model before using it to predict construction costs using the coefficient of determination and standard error of the mean square. If the accuracy of the model is not sufficiently high, it is essential to further analyze the data and/or change the selected factors.

4. Results

In this study, we aim to develop tools for managing investment construction projects that forecast expenses (budget), use artificial intelligence algorithms for cost forecasting,

identify the risk of cost overruns, and create recommendations to minimize them—a management decision support system in construction.

We analyzed references and identified the problem of cost overruns in 80% of construction projects worldwide, averaging approximately 20% of the original budget. By 2026, the budget overrun for bridge construction alone could reach approximately \$188.445 billion. The construction process is subject to unforeseen situations and changes that require constant monitoring and adaptation of design solutions to the current situation at construction sites, such as changes in design decisions, work schedules, technology, and inflation. An approach based on creating rigid links between documents and following the original plan is ineffective. It is necessary to develop a tool for creating multiple links with many degrees of freedom and options to find solutions approaching infinity and constantly analyze and predict the results to select the best scenario for adjusting plans.

Considering these findings, we propose an algorithm for predicting future costs based on an analysis of historical budget data and project characteristics, such as facility type, area, and structural elements. For example, a library of efficient solutions created using neural network algorithms allows the selection of an optimal set of resources, thereby improving planning quality. For this purpose, it is necessary to enter the values of the characteristics of a new project into the model to produce the predicted cost and amount of resources required for construction.

Building a budget management framework based on a mathematical model of multiple polynomial regression using the least-squares method is more accurate and reliable for managing investment project costs. The multiple polynomial regression model allows for the consideration of several independent variables, represented in the form of costs for the production of works as the product of the planned quantity by the unit price (materials, personnel, machinery, equipment, and overheads) and the linear shift coefficient as a given

value (e.g., profit, inflation). The LSM selects analogs when forecasting the cost of investment projects using artificial intelligence by minimizing the sum of the squares of deviations between the actual (historical) and planned (desired) values.

We proposed indicators of problems, such as the number of personnel and output, availability and supply of resources, and operating time of machines and mechanisms, to forecast the risk of deviation of the forecast value from the planned value and an algorithm based on the calculation of deviations from the plan-actual values. We compared the actual values with reference (planned) values accumulated through program services in a database such as PostgreSQL. In the case of deviations, the user is provided action recommendations depending on the risk level. For example, the system analyzes the number of labor resources involved, machines, and mechanisms in terms of the work schedule, signals critical deviations from planned values, and provides recommendations for redistributing resources (labor resources, machines, and mechanisms) between construction sites.

We propose methods for detailing information as the project develops, adapting existing detailing methods from LOD 100 to LOD 500 to compare planned and actual data to predict the risk of budget overruns.

Furthermore, to obtain accurate forecasting results, it is necessary to correctly select important characteristics that affect the cost of the project, to have a sufficiently large amount of historical data structured by the type of work and selected characteristics, to have a set of indicators and plan-fact deviations of values that will indicate the occurrence of risks, and to have a system consisting of complex hardware and software for automatic collection of information into a database for subsequent analysis and identification of risks that will become subjects for future studies.

5. Discussion

We propose a model based on the accumulated historical data on the number of resources involved in constructing facilities and their costs, implying that collecting data on projects with similar characteristics is necessary. Therefore, the tasks were divided into several parts.

First, it is necessary to propose a structure and model for storing information on projects that contain information about the characteristics to be incorporated into future models.

Second, it was necessary to define the set of characteristics to be included in the polynomial regression model. For this purpose, it is necessary to analyze and form several hypotheses and determine the most important characteristics that affect the cost of a project.

Technical characteristics of the project (e.g., structural elements, scope of work, and materials used).

Work technology (work rate, number of personnel, number of machines)

External factors (weather, economics, politics, and inflation).

Third, it is necessary to analyze existing digital technologies and propose an algorithm to automatically collect characteristics and data using IoT, computer vision, and machine learning, as well as to integrate these data.

Fourth, procedures should be proposed for implementing a new digital system for construction project management, including planning, motivation, accounting, and reporting. A new digital project management system should establish links between construction production and financial results. The system should automatically identify potential construction problems, evaluate the results, and propose an optimal solution using analytical tools and algorithms to minimize the risks.

Once the model is created, it forecasts the costs of new investment projects. Consequently, companies will improve the quality of project management and speed of

decision-making to ensure increased revenue and profit, productivity growth, and reduced production and project management costs.

6. Conclusions

The present study has shown that the application of artificial intelligence can provide a viable solution to complex problems in different industries, including construction. Specifically, the use of polynomial regression to predict construction costs has been demonstrated as an effective method for optimizing project planning and budgeting. The findings of this study have significant implications for both scientific research and practical applications, as they contribute to advancing the understanding of how artificial intelligence can be utilized to enhance decision-making processes in construction management.

Moreover, this study has provided insights into the potential limitations and challenges associated with the use of artificial intelligence in construction. Future research could explore alternative methods and models that may improve the accuracy and reliability of cost forecasting, as well as investigate the ethical and social implications of relying on automated decision-making systems in this field.

Overall, this study underscores the importance of embracing innovative technologies and approaches to address the complex challenges facing the construction industry. By leveraging the power of artificial intelligence, professionals in this field can enhance their ability to plan, execute, and deliver projects on time and within budget, ultimately contributing to the sustainable development of our built environment.

7. Notes

- The coefficient of determination (R^2) was used to determine how well the model distinguished the dependent variable (budget) from independent variables (technical characteristics, resource costs, etc.).
- Cost planning depended on the number of resources.
- Risk control was performed by monitoring the amount of resources.
- We performed numerous calculations and connections using artificial intelligence algorithms.
- Artificial intelligence for cost forecasting used a mathematical polynomial regression model.
- We use a mathematical polynomial regression model to predict the costs of the investment projects.
- We factored multiple characteristics into the mathematical model of polynomial regression.
- We used the LSM to predict the cost of analog selection.
- We used the coefficient of determination (R^2) to determine how well the model distinguished the dependent variable (budget) from the independent variables (technical characteristics, resource costs, etc.).

Declarations of interest

The author declares that she has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author used ChatGPT & Midjourney | AI bot in order to editor content. After using this tool/service, the author reviewed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Author Contribution

Natalia Leonidovna Breus: Conceptualization; Data curation; Formal analysis; Investigation; Methodology; Project administration; Resources; Software; Supervision; Validation; Visualization; Roles/Writing - original draft; and Writing - review & editing.

Data statement

The author confirms that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article.

References

- [1] Bridge Construction Market Report, 2022.
<https://www.thebusinessresearchcompany.com/report/bridge-construction-global-market-report> (accessed 21 September 2023).
- [2] Autodesk. <https://constructionblog.autodesk.com/construction-industry-statistics/> (accessed 12 September 2023).
- [3] M.A. Alkubati, N.A. Khalifa, H.A. Al-barakani, 2023. An overview of public transport reliability studies using a bibliometric analysis. *Ain Shams Eng. J.* 14, 101908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2022.101908>.
- [4] B.I. Steininger, M. Groth, B.L. Weber, 2020. Cost overruns and delays in infrastructure projects: The case of Stuttgart 21. 43, Working Paper. 11.
<https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1474961/FULLTEXT01.pdf>.
- [5] C.C. Cantarelli, E.J.E Molin, B. van Wee, B. Flyvbjerg, Characteristics of cost overruns for Dutch transport infrastructure projects and the importance of the decision to build and project phases, *Transp. Policy.* 22 (2012) 49–56.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2012.04.001>

- [6] J. Fortune, D. White, Framing of project critical success factors by a systems model, *Int. J. Proj. Manage.* 24 (2006) 53–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2005.07.004>
- [7] H.W. Kamran, A. Omran, S.B. Mohammed-Arshad, Bahrain. Risk management, capital adequacy and audit quality for financial stability: Assessment from commercial banks of Pakistan, *Asian Econ. Financ. Rev.* 9 (2019) 654–664 .
<https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.aefr.2019.96.654.664>
- [8] A. Nawaz, A. Waqar, S.A. Shah, M. Sajid, M.I. Khalid, An innovative framework for risk management in construction projects in developing countries: Evidence from Pakistan, *Risks.* 7 (2019) 24 <https://doi.org/10.3390/risks7010024>
- [9] M.A. Kallow, A.A. Bodla, A. Ejaz, R. Ishaq, How do risk management practices lead to project success in the construction industry? The mediated moderation of risk coping capacity and risk transparency, *Int. J. Constr. Manage.* 23 (2023) 2779–2787.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15623599.2022.2095719>
- [10] M. Abas, S.B. Khattak, T. Habib, U. Nadir, Assessment of critical risk and success factors in construction supply chain: A case of Pakistan, *Int. J. Constr. Manage.* 22 (2022) 2258–2266. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15623599.2020.1783597>
- [11] H. Kerzner, *Project Management Metrics, KPIs, and Dashboards: A Guide to Measuring and Monitoring Project Performance*, John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, New Jersey, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119427599>
- [12] M.W. Khan, Y. Ali, F. De Felice, A. Petrillo, Occupational health and safety in construction industry in Pakistan using modified-SIRA method, *Saf. Sci.* 118 (2019) 109–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2019.05.001>
- [13] M. Ajmair, Impact of industrial sector on GDP (Pakistan Case), *Eur. J. Contemp. Econ. Manag.* 1 (2014) 106. <https://doi.org/10.19044/elp.v1no1a8>

- [14] N. Breus, 2019. Cost accounting system using Internet of Things technologies as a tool to increase the productivity of work. *Econ. Yesterday Today Tomorrow*. 9–1, 203–209. https://elibrary.ru/download/elibrary_41860598_66025826.pdf (accessed 13 September 2023).
- [15] Aslam, B.; Maqsoom, A.; Inam, H.; Basharat, M.u.; Ullah, F. Forecasting Construction Cost Index through Artificial Intelligence. *Societies* 2023, 13, 219. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc13100219>
- [16] Park, D.; Yun, S. Construction Cost Prediction Using Deep Learning with BIM Properties in the Schematic Design Phase. *Appl. Sci.* 2023, 13, 7207. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13127207>
- [17] Pai, P., Wang, W. Using Machine Learning Models and Actual Transaction Data for Predicting Real Estate Prices. *Applied Sciences*, (2020), 5832, 10(17) [doi:10.3390/app10175832](https://doi.org/10.3390/app10175832)
- [18] Arkadij N. Larionov, Vyacheslav V. Solovev, Alexander A. Morozov, Moscow State University of Civil Engineering (National Research University) (MGSU); Moscow, Russian Federation; 2 LLC “APM”; Moscow, Russian Federation, DOI: 10.22227/1997-0935.2023.1.91-101
- [19] Makarov A.N., Gureev M.V., Determining the Parameters of a Model for Forecasting Material Resources for the Construction of Residential Buildings at the Investment Feasibility Assessment Stage, *CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTION* No. 4 (48) 2023 DOI: 10.54950/26585340_2023_4_97
- [20] ISO 19650:2018. Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) – Information management using building information modelling – Part 1: Concepts and principles. <https://www.iso.org/standard/68078.html> (accessed 19 August 2023).

- [21] BS 1192:2007+A2:2016. Collaborative production of architectural, engineering and construction information – Code of practice.
<https://knowledge.bsigroup.com/products/collaborative-production-of-architectural-engineering-and-construction-information-code-of-practice?version=standard>
(accessed 19 August 2023).
- [22] DIN EN ISO 19650-2:2019. Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) – Information management using building information modelling – Part 2: Delivery phase of the assets. <https://www.beuth.de/en/standard/din-en-iso-19650-2/304982454> (accessed 19 August 2023).
- [23] Matplotlib library in programming language Python.
<https://matplotlib.org/stable/gallery/mplot3d/surface3d.html> (accessed 12 September 2023).